

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) 1

Deliverable 10.2

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Executive Summary

The OH-FINE (Organic Farming Innovations Network Europe) project is dedicated to empowering European farmers through knowledge-sharing, training, and tools to improve organic agriculture. This first Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) provides a strategic framework for enhancing the visibility, accessibility, and long-term impact of OH-FINE's results, aligning with the EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy.

Communication focuses on making the project widely known, involving strategic outreach via digital platforms, printed materials, public events, and the media. The strategy is coordinated by SEAE and supported by project partners. Communication efforts aim to inform stakeholders, attract engagement, and demonstrate the impact of EU-funded research.

Dissemination ensures that project results are made publicly available. The plan involves distributing outputs like technical documents, educational materials, policy briefs, and videos through platforms like the Organic Farm Knowledge portal, OH-FINE website, EU FarmBook, and Organic Eprints as well as events and networking. Dissemination is carried out at local (via regional knowledge hubs) and EU-wide levels, with materials translated into multiple languages to ensure accessibility.

Exploitation involves turning results into practical tools, services, and policies that extend beyond the project's lifespan. This includes Key Exploitable Results (KERs) such as the Organic Farming Stakeholders Platform, Regional Knowledge Hubs, and Decision Support Systems. The plan details IP management, commercial pathways, and strategies for academic and public-good applications. Coordination among partners ensures effective use of results, with workshops and one-on-one consultations to refine exploitation routes.

The stakeholder mapping identifies diverse audiences, from conventional farmers to policymakers and consumers. OH-FINE uses a multi-actor approach to actively engage these groups, ensuring that communication and dissemination are relevant and impactful. Regional Hubs in Bulgaria, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, and Spain play a pivotal role in local engagement and knowledge exchange.

A robust evaluation framework with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) tracks the effectiveness of all CDEP activities. This includes targets for website traffic, social media engagement, video views, participation in events, number of publications, and stakeholder engagement.

The CDEP includes comprehensive handbooks that provide guidelines for partners on communication protocols, branding, open access, and the creation and sharing of educational materials. The document emphasizes transparency, collaboration, and the sustainability of OH-FINE's contributions to organic agriculture across Europe.

Disclaimer

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Abbreviations

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCP	Communication Contact Point
CDEP	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OFC	Organic Farming Learning Community
OH-FINE	Organic Farming Innovations Network Europe
RKH	Regional Knowledge Hubs
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SERI	Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation
SWOT	Strengths-Weaknesses-Opportunities-Threats-Analysis
WD	Working Days

1. Introduction

Authors: Laura Kemper and Barbara Schäfer (FiBL CH)

1.1 Background

Organic Farming Innovations Network Europe (OH-FINE) is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project funded under the Horizon Europe research and innovation framework program, that aims to empower European farmers through the definition, enhancement and transfer of competitive and efficient organic farming knowledge. OH-FINE will create a pan-European Organic Farming Learning Community to provide European farmers and smallholders with practice-oriented knowledge and tools for competitive organic agriculture.

Beyond the project, these future-oriented tools and networks will guide farmers during and after conversion to organic farming. In this way, OH-FINE will contribute to the EU's Farm to Fork Strategy, the Green Deal, the Biodiversity Strategy, and the EU Organic Action Plan's target of 25% of the total agricultural area to be farmed organically by 2030.

1.2 Communication, dissemination and exploitation defined

The success and lasting impact of a project strongly depend on three key objectives, on which work package 10, 11 and 12 (Sustainability, Communication, and Dissemination of Results 1, 2 and 3) will deliver on:

- To make the project known to relevant stakeholders by ensuring an effective execution of communication activities and promoting the project through diverse channels.
- To provide easy access to information and results on the website and disseminate the project findings through customised materials in all partner countries.
- To secure the project's legacy and long-term accessibility of its outcomes.

Communication, dissemination and exploitation play an important role in achieving these objectives. These three branches work together to ensure that the project and its results are visible, accountable and useful to the public and our key target groups.

This document, the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP), outlines a clearly structured strategy and action plan by integrating the concepts of communication, dissemination and exploitation¹:

- "Communication can be defined as taking strategic and targeted measures to inform, promote and communicate the project itself, its activities and results to a wide range of audiences, including the media and the general public, and possibly to engage in a two-way exchange." The communication activities of Horizon Europe projects must focus on demonstrating the benefits and impact of EU-funded research and innovation activities (European Commission, 2024 a).

¹ The definitions of communication, dissemination and exploitation are in accordance with the EU guidance on Horizon Europe projects: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

- “Dissemination can be defined as making the results available to the public by appropriate means (other than by protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publication in any medium” (European Commission, 2024 a).
- “Exploitation can be defined as the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the project concerned, including, among others, commercial exploitation such as the development, creation, production and marketing of a product or process, the creation and provision of a service, or standardisation activities. Exploitation can involve project partners themselves using the project results, as well as external user groups” (European Commission, 2024 a).

1.3 Communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy

The CDEP strategy will follow the key stages of the AIDA model: Awareness to attract the attention of the target audience, Interest and Desire of the target audience to know more about the project, and Action to lead the target audience towards involvement in the project and promotion of its results to facilitate exploitation.

The CDEP outlines how we plan to achieve these objectives as well as specific objective 5 from the Grant Agreement: “To maximize outreach and beneficial influence of the project results and reach the target users (AKIS) through an effectively established communication and dissemination plan, including innovative training capsules” (OH-FINE Grant Agreement, Part B – Page 4).

Communication, dissemination and exploitation are intertwined and it is often not possible to distinguish key components or tasks between the three. The communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies are explained in detail below. In addition, some components are equally relevant for all three, including:

- Active contribution of all partners and all work packages to ensure optimal dissemination, communication and exploitation of project results.
- Translation of materials where deemed useful and distribution of materials in the countries represented in the project.
- Active engagement with all stakeholder groups.
- A reporting tracker to track all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities to ensure that the objectives and KPIs of the project are met (see Annex 2, section 8.2).
- Adherence to the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) dimensions at their capabilities, ensuring open science, public engagement, and gender equality.

OH-FINE is also committed to implementing the multi-actor approach. The multi-actor approach, part of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), aims to make research results more demand-driven and socially relevant. It goes beyond simply sharing results or consulting stakeholders and ensures the active involvement of a wide range of actors in line with the project's objectives. This approach allows for easier acceptance and adoption of new ideas, methods and solutions developed within the project (European Commission, 2024 b).

1.4 About this deliverable

The CDEP is a living document that will be monitored and updated throughout the project in response to feedback, new information, trends and other factors such as collaborations with other research projects or stakeholders.

This document outlines OH-FINEs communication, dissemination and exploitation plan and the communication and dissemination handbooks (in the annex). The CDEP is a resource for all project partners, as it provides:

- A preliminary stakeholder mapping and overview of target audiences (section 2).
- A description of the communication strategy (section 3).
- An outline of the dissemination strategy and objectives (section 0).
- An explanation of the exploitation strategy and definition of boundaries in terms of exploitation and inclusion of exploitation guidelines (section 5).
- The communication handbook, which includes communication procedures and templates (Annex 1)
- The dissemination handbook, which includes a description of the different dissemination tools, formats and channels as well as guidelines and templates for all dissemination materials (Annex 2).

OH-FINE partners can contact work packages 10, 11 and 12 leaders for any questions or comments regarding communication, dissemination and exploitation (any changes to these contacts will be communicated to partners via the Executive Board):

- Communication manager: Aina Calafat Rogers (SEAE)
- Dissemination manager: Laura Kemper and Barbara Schäfer (both FiBL CH)
- Exploitation manager: Ángel Adell (EURADIA-BETANIA)

2. Stakeholder mapping

Authors: Laura Kemper and Barbara Schäfer (FiBL CH)

To ensure maximal impact of the project, OH-FINE will share outputs with several target audiences, namely (as defined in the Grant Agreement):

- Conventional farmers
- Pre- and in-conversion farmers
- Post-conversion organic farmers
- Advisors
- Policy makers
- Input suppliers
- Agri-food Value Chain Operators
- Education/Academic Community
- Scientific Community

- Consumers and Citizens

The OH-FINE project is a multi-actor project, targeting many different audiences for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities on both the regional/national and European level. In the context of the multi-actor approach, the project must ensure sufficient and active engagement of the different stakeholder groups, while the outputs need to address different audiences in appropriate ways.

Some stakeholders will be directly involved in the project activities, where they can contribute their knowledge, experience and perspectives to the project outcomes. Many of the actors in this group will be practitioners, such as farmers, advisors, the education community, policy makers and researchers. These actors are considered as end-users of the project results. These stakeholders will be the primary target groups of the practice- and policy-oriented outputs intended for dissemination and exploitation.

Regional and national stakeholder networks will be established or expanded in Bulgaria, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland and Spain, which will establish regional hubs. Mapping these networks and engaging with them will be the subject of Tasks 2.2, 2.3, 8.2 and 9.1 led by TEAGASC. Stakeholder networks in the other project countries will be engaged through educational materials, cross visits, fora and other events and networking activities.

In addition, consumers and citizens will be engaged primarily through communication and awareness raising activities.

During the course of the OH-FINE project, a stakeholder platform will be set up as part of the ICT platform to allow different stakeholder groups to interact, contribute and use the project results. This platform will further promote the multi-actor approach and allow easy and efficient interaction and involvement in the project.

Table 1 lists and describes the stakeholder groups defined in the Grant Agreement, and how we plan to engage the different groups throughout the project.

This stakeholder overview will be complemented by the work carried out in work packages 2, 8 and 9 to analyse the structure of the overall Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) and to define the specific knowledge needs of the different stakeholders.

Table 1: Overview of OH-FINE target audiences

Main groups of target audience	Composition, characteristics and needs of target audience	OH-FINE expectation of target audience	Level of CDE engagement with target audience			OH-FINE tools to reach target audience	Value added by OH-FINE
			Aware of the project	Involved in project and/or regional hub	Use project outputs		
Conventional Farmers	Conventional farmers who are interested in increasing their awareness and skills in adopting sustainable/organic practices. Conventional farmers often require detailed information about the benefits and processes involved in organic farming.	End-users of practical outputs to improve farm profitability and sustainability Participate in OH-FINE training, workshops, field demonstrations, farmer networks and learning communities Provide input about current knowledge and networks	XXX	XXX	XXX	Workshops, training and advisory services; Field demonstrations; Educational materials; Cross visits	Increased awareness and skills for adopting sustainable methods.
Pre- and in-conversion farmers	Pre- and in-conversion farmers who are interested in a clearer understanding and smoother transition to organic farming. Farmers in the process of converting require specific technical advice on organic farming practices, soil management, pest control, and crop rotation.	End-users of practical outputs to improve farm profitability and sustainability Participate in OH-FINE training, workshops, field demonstrations, farmer networks and learning communities Provide input about current knowledge and networks	XXX	XXX	XXX	Workshops, training and advisory services; Field demonstrations; Mentorship from experienced organic farmers; Educational materials; Cross visits	Clearer understanding and smoother transition to organic farming and skills for adopting sustainable methods.

Main groups of target audience	Composition, characteristics and needs of target audience	OH-FINE expectation of target audience	Level of CDE engagement with target audience			OH-FINE tools to reach target audience	Value added by OH-FINE
			Aware of the project	Involved in project and/or regional hub	Use project outputs		
Post-conversion organic farmers	Organic farmers who are interested in improved farm sustainability and market competitiveness. Post-conversion, farmers need advanced knowledge in organic farming techniques to enhance productivity and sustainability.	End-users of practical outputs to improve farm profitability and sustainability Participate in OH-FINE training, workshops, field demonstrations, farmer networks and learning communities Provide input about current knowledge and networks	XXX	XXX	XXX	Workshops, training and advisory services; Field demonstrations; Mentorship from experienced organic farmers; Educational materials; Cross visits	Improved farm sustainability and market competitiveness.
Advisors	Farm advisors who are interested in improving their advisory service and knowledge skills in organic agriculture. Advisors need up-to-date information on organic farming practices, tools for effective farmer engagement, and capacity-building resources.	End-users of practical outputs to improve farm profitability and sustainability Participate in OH-FINE training, workshops, field demonstrations, farmer networks and learning communities Provide input about needs	XXX	XX	XXX	Specialized training course; Educational materials; Participation in knowledge exchange networks; Cross visits	More effective and comprehensive advisory services.

Main groups of target audience	Composition, characteristics and needs of target audience	OH-FINE expectation of target audience	Level of CDE engagement with target audience			OH-FINE tools to reach target audience	Value added by OH-FINE
			Aware of the project	Involved in project and/or regional hub	Use project outputs		
Policymakers (EU, national and regional)	Including key officials from the European Commission as well as relevant ministries, competent authorities and administrative bodies at national and regional level. Policy makers need Information to improve knowledge exchange and sustainability in agricultural sector. Data and insights on effective sustainable farming practices and barriers.	End-users of policy briefs, reports, and direct exchange to provide better informed policies supporting sustainable agriculture.	X	X	X	Policy briefs, reports; Direct engagement in forums and consultations	Better-informed policies supporting sustainable agriculture.
Input suppliers*	Aligned regional and European supply chain to support sustainable practices.	Participate in workshops and information sessions	X	X	X	Workshops; Information sessions	Aligned supply chain supporting sustainable practices.
Agri-food value chain operators*	Regional and European operators in the agri-food value chain from production to consumption. They need Information on organic farming trends, consumer preferences, and sustainable supply chain practices.	End-users of different project outputs. Participate in workshops and collaboration opportunities	X	X	X	Workshops; Collaboration opportunities	More sustainable and efficient value chains.

Main groups of target audience	Composition, characteristics and needs of target audience	OH-FINE expectation of target audience	Level of CDE engagement with target audience			OH-FINE tools to reach target audience	Value added by OH-FINE
			Aware of the project	Involved in project and/or regional hub	Use project outputs		
Educational/academic community**	Regional and European educational and academic communities and institutions, who are interested in sustainable agricultural practices and market competitiveness. They need educational resources on organic farming and sustainable agricultural practices.	End-users of OH-FINE outputs, especially the educational materials.	X		X	Academic publications; Conferences; Educational materials	Enhanced educational and research opportunities.
Scientific community**	International scientific community, especially researchers working in the field of sustainable and organic agriculture, and/or in other related projects. They need access to current research, data on organic farming practices, and collaboration opportunities.	End-users of OH-FINE's scientific papers.	X		X	Scientific journal articles	Informed scientific research contributing to agricultural innovation.

Main groups of target audience	Composition, characteristics and needs of target audience	OH-FINE expectation of target audience	Level of CDE engagement with target audience			OH-FINE tools to reach target audience	Value added by OH-FINE
			Aware of the project	Involved in project and/or regional hub	Use project outputs		
Consumers & citizens***	A diverse group of individuals and consumer organisations, both regionally and across Europe, representing different social and professional backgrounds with a common interest in food, farming and the environment. Their priority is an increased awareness of the benefits of organic farming and understanding of sustainable food choices.	Awareness of the project and increased understanding of the environmental and health benefits of sustainable practices.	X	X	X	Public campaigns; Social media; Community engagement activities	Increased demand for and support of sustainable agricultural products.

X= minor; XX = medium; XXX = strong

* For the purposes of some OH-FINE activities (e.g., AKIS workshops), the input suppliers and Agri-food value chain operators stakeholder groups will not be differentiated.

** For the purposes of some OH-FINE activities (e.g., AKIS workshops), the educational/academic community and scientific community stakeholder groups will not be differentiated.

*** To further reinforce the planned dissemination activities, Cittadinanzattiva-ACN will work to involve national associations interested in the topic, with particular attention to the consumer associations of Bulgaria, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland and Spain. These may be joined by other citizens' associations that are part of the constituency of Cittadinanzattiva's European network, such as [Eco Club UNWE](#), [Saugok save](#), the [Polish Green Network and the Association of Adult Education Centres of Extremadura -AUPEX](#).

3. Communication strategy

Author: Aina Calafat Rogers (SEAE)

This plan aims to facilitate coordination and information exchange in the project team (internally) and with the EU Agency, as well as ensure best quality, efficiency and coherence on all communication-related activities.

The main goals of communication are to engage relevant stakeholders and attract them to collaborate and get involved in the project, and to inform the wider public on how public money is spent, as well as to raise awareness on the importance and success of European collaboration.

To achieve this, multidisciplinary communication channels will be used for interactive feedback loops via e-promotion (websites, social media), printed materials (posters, leaflets), mass media (articles, press releases) and events (webinars, presentations).

The communication activities at the project level will be complemented with the partners' networks and online/offline communication channels to reach regional and local target groups and also increase cost-efficiency.

Additionally, spreading the information at the EU level is especially important for building the OH-FINE Organic Farming Stakeholders' Platform. In the case of the 5 countries with Regional Knowledge Hubs, extra communication activities will be required at the national level.

The following sections outline the key components of the communications strategy.

3.1 Communication roles, responsibilities and tracking

Communication activities are led by the SEAE, in coordination with the project coordination team at CSIC and the WP11 and WP12 leader, FiBL CH.

All other project partners are actively involved in the preparation of communication materials. Each partner will identify two Communication Contact Points (CCP) whose contact details will be listed and uploaded in the SACO platform. For more about the role and responsibilities of CCPs, see section 7.3.2.

A communication handbook will be shared with the consortium (see annex 1). To ensure close and smooth cooperation with all project partners, quarterly meetings will be held with the WP11 and WP12 leaders, the project coordinators and the rest of the partners.

In addition to the provisions of this plan, concrete communication actions will be planned and programmed in advance.

To keep track of the communication activities carried out, all partners will record them in the "reporting tracker" in the "communications" table (see section 8.2)

If partners present the OH-FINE project at fairs, conferences or other events, the affected partner will lead the planning, preparation and implementation. SEAE and the rest of the consortium will provide support as needed.

For written materials, such as press releases and articles, the partners will include the funding logos and the disclaimer and each of the partners will be responsible for the final quality of

the material. For all major publications in English, the SEAE will prepare the drafts and FiBL CH and CSIC, as well as other partners (depending on content) will be involved in the final revision before the material is published to ensure a transparent sign-off.

In general, all material will be prepared in English first. The majority of communication materials will be developed by SEAE, with support from FiBL CH and input from partners (especially from CSIC as project coordinator) and then shared with all partners for final approval before being published or distributed. Translation, where necessary, will be done by the respective partners for targeted distribution. SEAE will ensure that timelines for input from the partners are communicated in advance.

In case communication material is only relevant for a specific country or sector (e.g. a press release on a regional meeting/activity), only those partners will be actively involved. These partners should add all materials to the “04 Publications-for-review” folder on the SACO platform at least 15 days prior to publication. Where applicable, materials should be sent to CSIC as project coordinator in advance.

Each partner has an allocated budget for the aforementioned contribution as outlined in the project grant agreement.

3.2 Communication materials and channels

In order to reach a broad public on the one hand and specific target groups in various countries on the other hand, different materials and distribution channels are used.

The project’s visual identity has been developed starting with a logo that synthesizes the main concept of the project in an image.

The corporate typography has been established in line with the logo. The templates and communication and dissemination materials were designed accordingly, and shared with all partners.

The communication tools and guidelines are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2: Communication tools and guidelines

Tools	Description
Project identity kit	Project branding, including logo Templates for internal and external communication materials Guidelines: GDPR Compliance
Informative and visually appealing materials	A promotional video describing the project’s goals and activities. It will be subtitled in all of the project partners’ languages. A poster/rollup describing the project’s goals and activities in all of the project partners’ languages. A leaflet describing the project’s goals and activities in all of the project partners’ languages.

Digital infopack	Infographics adapted to different target audiences and translated into the project's countries languages.
Public website	https://www.oh-fine.eu/
Social media platforms	Project's description, activities and milestones will be shared through social media (at least LinkedIn and Instagram)
Press releases	Press releases and digital campaigns will be used to announce and promote the activities and main milestones
Public factsheets	Public factsheets on general aspects to engage target audiences will be released
Partners' channels	Partners existing communication channels such as their websites, newsletters, social media and networks, will be used to enhance communication
Participation in events	Various events including the European Researchers Night and Science week
Communication handbook	The handbook includes guidelines on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the use of the project and funding logos in all communication activities • the project's identity • the use of the project's communication materials • the templates • the use of the project's social media and partner's social media and communication channels.

The project website will be the main information hub for the project. It will provide key details about the project, including news and upcoming events. It will also ensure easy, fast and open access to the project's publications, as well as communication, dissemination and promotion materials.

The OH-FINE project website will be continuously updated to ensure that the broader public is continuously informed on project activities and results. All partners are responsible for contributing news, events and other updates to keep the website up-to-date. For more information about the website, see deliverable 10.1.

The project will also have its own social media channels, which will use English as it is the *lingua franca* between all partners. However, suitable platforms will be also created and managed in each sub-network by OFISET, TEAGASC, WULS, BIOSELENA, LEUA, FiBL AT, EV ILVO to overcome the language and cultural gap for end-users and reach local stakeholders. Each regional hub will establish channels that work best for their region. They will work closely with WP10-12 to ensure the most relevant project information is made available via these platforms, in their local languages. They will also provide WP10-12 with

relevant information to be dissemination through the project channels. The procedures for this will be established once the hubs have been fully set up.

All partners will also make sure they use their own communication channels to communicate the project and its results widely. This will include their institutional websites, newsletters and social media as well as articles in the specialised press. The project heavily relies on all partners to use their established networks and communication channels in a very focused approach to have the greatest possible outreach in a cost-effective way in their country.

In addition to the project partners, regional stakeholders will be identified to strengthen communication activities and reach a broader public using the snowball strategy.

Specialized journals and discussion forums will also be used to spread selected information to certain target groups. Partners will also attend events to promote the project and engage stakeholders.

3.3 Evaluation

Key performance indicators (KPIs) have been agreed upon for the various communication activities (Table 3). The KPIs will be monitored regularly to ensure that there are no deviations.

Table 3: Evaluation of communication activities and implementation of the plan.

Activities and tools	KPIs
Project identity kit with project branding, poster, templates for internal and external materials and guidelines for partners	Project logo, project poster in all project partners' languages, book of styles, included in the Communication Handbook
Informative and visually appealing materials such as brochures, presentations, and videos that explain project goals, methodologies, and outcomes.	Promotional video subtitled in all project partners' languages. Brochure in all project languages. At least 300 views for the video and >2.000 copies of the brochures distributed
Digital info-pack for stakeholders to inform them and their communities about the challenges and benefits of OH-FINE. Mainly based on infographics to reach different stakeholders, targeting especially primary producers, traders, certification companies, consumers and local/regional authorities.	1 general info-pack produced in M6-M18 translated into the project's countries languages
Public Website with a description of the challenges addressed by the project, its consortium, its objectives and solutions; a cluster section with a list of related projects; a news section; a resource section	> 2000 visitors, 75 items published

with project’s material; a contact form; and OH-FINE social media

Social media platforms will be used to share project updates, success stories, and relevant news, engaging with a wider online audience. Specific social media accounts for the project will be established in LinkedIn and Instagram, keeping strong interaction with the consortium partners’ channels. Sharing the project content in the already established networks to ensure a higher impact and reaching a larger number of experts and stakeholders. Cluster projects and citizens associations will be contacted and connections to their social media will be established, for networking and disseminating the project contents even further.

Social media engagement: >20 posts >500 views

Press releases will be issued to announce major project milestones, partnerships, and breakthroughs, gaining media coverage. Digital campaigns to promote project progress and results will be planned. The campaigns will be promoted through the project’s website, social networks and dissemination events. Press Releases will emphasize the project vision and key results and outputs.

2 communication campaigns, each including: 3% increase in followers, 3 articles in popular press, 1 press release

Public factsheets about the project to reach different target audiences

> 50 subscribers

Promotion through partners existing communication channels such as their websites, social networks accounts, etc.

> 5000 people will be reached through various communication channels, ensuring at least 1,000 attendees in total of the different dissemination events developed along the project

Participation in events

5 Universities involved in the European European Researchers’ Night
8 events (1 in each country) during the Science week

4. Dissemination strategy

Authors: Laura Kemper and Barbara Schäfer (FiBL CH)

Dissemination activities build on and connect closely to communication activities to ensure a reliable, seamless, and efficient transfer of OH-FINE knowledge and tools to targeted actors, users, and beneficiaries. To achieve this, the consortium established a comprehensive dissemination strategy in line with the stakeholder mapping as well as a clear dissemination handbook for partners (see annex 2), outlining the different responsibilities and procedures. The key components of the dissemination strategy are outlined in the following sections.

4.1 Multi-directional and multi-level knowledge transfer coordinated with partners

The project will target audiences both at the regional level and the European level. At the local level, regional hubs will act as local centres for knowledge exchange and training, tailored to the specific needs of the different regions. This will serve to 1) gather stakeholder input in order to make sure project tools and knowledge are meeting their needs, and 2) disseminate information and best practices tailored to regional specificities and in local languages.

Dissemination at the European level will be facilitated through the project website, the Organic Farm Knowledge platform, the three project fora, collaboration with other European projects, dissemination through European-level networks (see section 4.2), the ICT tool, and English language resources, including practice abstracts, videos, technical documents, and policy briefs.

At both levels, the stakeholder profiles outlined in Table 1 will be taken into consideration in order to reach all target audiences effectively.

4.2 A wide range of practical dissemination tools, formats and channels

A number of tools and formats will be used to disseminate the OH-FINE results to the target audiences. These include:

- Educational materials: Videos, technical documents and practice abstracts, and policy briefs.
- Articles in specialised press and peer-reviewed journals
- Peer reviewed scientific articles and publications
- OH-FINE workshops, cross visits, information sessions, seminars, fora and other events
- Field demonstrations
- Targeted training programs and specialized training courses
- Mentorship from experienced organic farmers
- Participating in networking events and knowledge-exchange networks, industry conferences and workshops, scientific conferences and symposiums, agricultural fairs and other relevant events.
- Partnerships with educational institutions

- Research collaborations

Educational materials will have a strong focus on best practices and barriers to conversion, thus supporting farmers in their conversion to organic. All educational materials and other relevant materials will be translated to partner languages and made available on several platforms:

- **Organic Farm Knowledge:** The platform is well established among farmers and advisors across Europe and already contains a wealth of information about organic best practices. The toolbox will allow users to easily find OH-FINE materials relevant for them, in multiple languages. The platform is available at <https://organic-farmknowledge.org/>
- **OH-FINE ICT tool:** The tool will be populated with OH-FINE materials as well as other official data sources in order to create a Decision Support System to support farmers with decision making related to conversion and organic farming practices.
- **OH-FINE website:** All educational materials will be showcased on the project website. The website is: <https://www.oh-fine.eu/>
- **EU CAP Network:** The website features a page about the OH-FINE project, which will include all practice abstracts as well as links to other relevant project materials. The page is available here: https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/organic-farming-innovations-network-europe_en
- **EU FarmBook:** The platform was created to help get practical knowledge from EU-funded research projects “into the hands of the farmers, foresters and advisors across Europe.” The OH-FINE project has already been registered on the EU FarmBook. Videos, documents and other practice-oriented material will be adapted to the standards of the platform, taking into account the limit to the file size and the files formats that are compatible with the EU FarmBook platform. Metadata will fit with the FarmBook’s requirements. The platform is available here: <https://welcome.eufarmbook.eu/>
- Other relevant platforms where relevant.

The educational materials will also be used and disseminated by partners and regional hubs. Integrating these materials into partners’ work and their networks will also ensure that the materials are used beyond the lifetime of the project so they can have a lasting impact. They will also be disseminated through social media. The regional hubs will set up their own dissemination channels managed by OFISET, TEAGASC, WULS, BIOSELENA, LEUA, FiBL AT and EV ILVO. These channels will make it possible to overcome the language and cultural gap for the end users.

Efforts will also be made to coordinate with related projects to include OH-FINE outputs in their platforms. For example, the OrganicAdviceNetwork project will create several e-learning courses that could potentially include OH-FINE educational materials.

To ensure knowledge transmission with the scientific and technical community, **scientific publications** will be submitted to peer-reviewed journals and stored in the open-access repository Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>). Where relevant, publications will also be stored in Organic Eprints (<https://orgprints.org/>). Likewise, **articles in specialised press, field demonstrations**, presentations at the **OH-FINE Fora, workshops**, conferences and other events will widely showcase the project’s results. Where relevant, these will also be stored in Zenodo and Organic Eprints.

Table 1 explains which tools will be primarily used to reach the different target audiences.

A detailed introduction to the different educational materials, guidelines for partners and templates can be found in the dissemination handbook in annex 2.

4.3 Exchange with other relevant Horizon Europe projects

In order to reach a broader audience and avoid duplicating efforts made in related projects, OH-FINE will work closely with other Horizon Europe projects, especially those funded under HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20, HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1, and HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3. In task 10.6, we will analyse each project's objectives and methodologies to identify synergies and mutual benefits. Coordinators of beneficiary projects will be contacted to provide detailed insights into their objectives and planned activities, as well as to introduce them to the OH-FINE project. This will help pinpoint areas for collaboration, such as joint workshops, cross-field visits, stakeholder meetings, training activities, networking, and collective policy recommendations. A collaborative dissemination strategy will enhance the visibility and impact of findings. A long-term sustainability plan will ensure continued collaboration beyond the project timeline, in line with EU goals for organic agriculture.

4.4 Open access to project results to ensure long-term availability

To ensure open access and long-term availability of project outputs, we have set up an OH-FINE community on Zenodo. Where relevant, partners can also upload materials to Organic Eprints. Both platforms allow users to easily link materials to the project and ensure materials will be available long-term.

All scientific publications will be open access upon publication. Gold open access (immediate open access through the publisher) is strongly encouraged but in some cases, green open access (open access through self-archiving) may be used to ensure that publications are open access. In either case, OH-FINE partners will deposit the final peer-reviewed manuscript in the OH-FINE community on Zenodo and, where relevant, on Organic Eprints.

To ensure open access and long-term availability, educational materials will be published on several additional platforms (see section 4.2 for more information).

For more information about using Zenodo and Organic Eprints, see annex 2 (sections 8.7 and 8.8).

For more information about open access and long-term availability are also included in D1.2 – Data Management Plan.

4.5 Comprehensive tracking of educational materials

Topics for technical documents, practice abstracts and videos are being defined by partners and entered into the “dissemination tracker” – a tracking document to organise the work being done on the different educational materials. The dissemination tracker lists the rough topic of the material, who is responsible for drafting it and the general timeline. There is also a section to track the progress of the document and a checklist of the various steps that need to be completed in order to publish and disseminate the different materials. More information about the tracker and the specific steps for partners are available in annex 2.

The policy briefs will be defined as the project progresses and will be included in the dissemination tracker.

4.6 Training and support for partners related to educational materials

OH-FINE partners will receive basic training and support from WP10/11/12 in order to produce effective educational materials that reach target audiences and are in line with OH-FINE procedures and project design. This will begin with a video webinar in spring 2025 that will inform partners about tips and tricks for planning and filming videos as well as what support and processes are in place in WP10/11/12. Templates and guidance will also be produced by WP10 for technical documents, practice abstracts, videos, presentations and policy briefs in order to support partners.

4.7 Evaluation

Key performance indicators (KPIs) have been agreed upon for the various dissemination activities (Table 4). The KPIs will be monitored regularly to ensure that there are no deviations.

Table 4: Evaluation of dissemination activities and implementation of the dissemination plan.

Activities and tools	KPIs
A comprehensive database of existing resources and knowledge on organic farming practices.	Over 1,000 active users accessed and utilized the database within the first two years, with a continual increase in user engagement and resource diversity.
Three forums	>At least 50 attendees at each one
Publications (scientific and non-scientific)	>3 peer-reviewed papers >15 articles in specialized press
Training and dissemination material	>40 practice abstracts (EIP-AGRI) >30 dissemination videos >15 technical documents >26 videos of field trials >26 technical documents of field trials >Produce and distribute at least 50 different types of materials, reaching at least 5,000 producers >Produce a minimum of 30 comprehensive dissemination documents, each receiving at least 500 downloads/views and 10 citations >Of all the videos that will be produced during the project, we will produce 23 videos of 1m and 30" duration, as well as a 15" version. All of them will receive a total of 120,000 views.
Training and workshops	>8 cross visits >24 technical workshops

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >24 field demonstrations >20 community events >ensure at least 1,000 attendees in total across all dissemination events
Organic Farming Stakeholder Platform	>Engage at least 200 distinct stakeholders across Europe, with regular monthly interactions and high satisfaction ratings in feedback surveys.
Clustering with other projects	>10 new collaborative partnerships
Policy briefs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >3 policy briefs >1 guide with conclusions and recommendations >3 policy recommendations adopted with the engagement of 25+ policymakers >Contribution to at least 1 policy changes or new initiatives at local, regional, or national levels
Decision Support System (DSS) ICT Tool	>Over 500 active users with a satisfaction score of 4.5 out of 5 within six months post-launch
Collaboration with EIP-Agri operational groups and other projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Minimum of 5 collaborative workshops, seminars, or meetings >Dissemination reach: aim for an audience reach of over 1,000 individuals across at least 5 different EU countries, with engagement metrics like downloads, shares, or active participation in events
Fairs	>Participation in at least 4 fairs
Reports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Report describing the AKIS and making recommendations to facilitate greater adoption of organic farming >Report on the project's impact on the competitiveness of farms >1 guide on the implementation of the innovative project methodology to maintain optimal results

5. Exploitation strategy

Authors: Ángel Adell and Isabel Álvarez-Rico (EURADIA-BETANIA)

OH-FINE encompasses various tasks, including the development and execution of a robust, industry-focused exploitation plan and the management of pertinent intellectual property rights (IPR). This approach is crucial to enable the dissemination of OH-FINE's outcomes, along with the tools and models crafted, to permeate the market and ensure the work done can have impact beyond the project lifetime. This document elucidates the initial version of the exploitation plan, which serves as an initial blueprint for potential exploitation endeavours. In this deliverable we will delve into some of the possible opportunities and strategies for harnessing the project's results.

Effectively capitalizing on OH-FINE's outcomes necessitates the formulation of operational strategies and commercialisation pathways, not only for individual project results but also for the collective project outcomes. Coordination of individual exploitation plans is imperative to forestall conflicts, and these strategies must remain agile and adaptable, aligning with evolving market dynamics and technological trends. The exploitation strategy entails the preparation of a preliminary roadmap for utilizing and potentially commercializing OH-FINE's results, focusing on market adoption, licensing opportunities, and integration into existing agricultural frameworks to maximize impact and sustainability.

The preliminary exploitation plan for each partner is outlined in section 2.2 of the OH-FINE project proposal. This section details how partners will utilize project outcomes during and after the project. During implementation, the strategy focuses on developing, validating, and demonstrating knowledge, technologies, and tools for organic farming. Demonstrative use cases, combined with dissemination and marketing efforts, will promote stakeholder adoption. Strategic partnerships with farmers, industry, research institutions, and policymakers will be strengthened to ensure long-term impact.

This section presents the Initial Exploitation Plan, including a potential Key Exploitable Results (KERs) characterization table and a Risk Assessment Map, both of which will be continuously refined and consolidated in D12.1 (Exploitation Plan). A dedicated workshop in month 36 will further shape the final exploitation plan based on project outcomes.

5.1 Description of Key Exploitable Results

According to the EC glossary of terms of the Funding and Tenders Opportunities, the results of a project are defined as “any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.”

Key Exploitable Results (KERs) refer to the most significant outputs generated by a project that have potential for further use, commercialization, or societal impact. These results can be scientific, technological, or methodological innovations, and they contribute to the overall objectives of the funded research. It basically includes all the output generated during the project, which can create impact during and/or after the funded project period and which could be used either by the project partners or by other stakeholders. Under Horizon Europe, project partners must define how they will exploit KERs after the project ends. This includes:

- Commercial exploitation (e.g., patents, spin-offs, technology licensing)
- Scientific dissemination (e.g., academic publications, open science initiatives)
- Policy integration (e.g., recommendations to influence regulation)
- Public good usage (e.g., open-access tools, training resources for stakeholders)

5.1.1 OH-FINE potential Exploitable Results Summary

The initial potential Key Exploitable Results at the consortium level were identified during the drafting of the project as follows:

- Organic Farming Stakeholders Platform.

- Policy Recommendations and Guides.
- Organic Farming Regional Knowledge Hubs.
- Digital Decision Support System (DSS) for Organic Farming.
- Comprehensive Training and Educational Materials.

The first three have been preliminarily analysed and are outlined below. These results and analysis may change during the implementation of the project. Other potential exploitable results will be identified and analysed throughout the project.

Exploitable Results Analysis

Organic Farming Stakeholders Platform

Description	A centralised digital hub connecting farmers, researchers, policymakers, and consumers.
Problems Addressed & Alternative Solutions	Problem: Lack of a unified, knowledge-sharing community for organic farming. Alternative Solutions: Dispersed forums, farmer cooperatives, industry conferences.
Innovation Compared to Existing Solutions	Matchmaking for networking, knowledge-sharing tools, integration with decision-support tools.
Unique Selling Point	The only platform connecting all organic farming stakeholders in one ecosystem.
Potential Competitors	EIT Food, existing organic farming networks, but none with an integrated ICT-based approach.

Policy Recommendations and Guides

Description	Comprehensive policy documents supporting organic farming-friendly legislation.
Problems Addressed & Alternative Solutions	Problem: Gaps in supportive policies for organic transition. Alternative Solutions: Individual lobbying, fragmented policy recommendations.
Innovation Compared to Existing Solutions	Data-driven, field-tested recommendations for EU policymakers.
Unique Selling Point	3 Policy briefs with recommendations for policy makers to influence future policy and regulatory actions will be elaborated compiling the main conclusions of the project

	and presented to the correspondent competent authorities. The policy briefs will be tailored with real-time farmer feedback and based on market and industry trends.
Potential Competitors	Think tanks, FAO, EU research bodies.

Organic Farming Regional Knowledge Hubs

Description	Physical and digital centres offering localized training, networking, and advisory services.
Problems Addressed & Alternative Solutions	Problem: Lack of localized organic farming support. Alternative Solutions: Individual consultants, academic research centres.
Innovation Compared to Existing Solutions	Community-driven, real-time access to organic experts.
Unique Selling Point	First region-specific organic knowledge hubs integrating digital and physical support.
Potential Competitors	Traditional agricultural extension services, private consulting firms.

5.1.2 Key Exploitable Results for Non-profit and Research Institutions

This section focuses on the exploitation of results by research institutions and non-profit organizations. Unlike commercial entities, these organizations will leverage project outcomes to increase funding through grants, research projects, or patents, rather than directly developing marketable products. Key benefits include:

- Expanding research portfolios and publications.
- Strengthening networks with institutions and researchers.
- Transferring expertise and methodologies to similar projects.
- Developing educational resources such as workshops and courses.

The OH-FINE project will enhance the knowledge base of non-profits and their networks, foster new collaborations, and create networking opportunities through events and conferences. This engagement will support future initiatives, broaden institutional impact, and drive long-term sustainability in relevant fields.

5.2 OH-FINE IPR Management

Horizon Europe projects prioritize impact and innovation in science, economy, and society, requiring strategic technologies to drive growth and competitiveness. To achieve this,

innovation management, intellectual property rights (IPR) management, and exploitation management must be carefully coordinated.

Key Aspects of IPR Management in OH-FINE

- **Ownership & Joint Development:** Under Horizon Europe regulations, the partner generating results retains ownership. In cases of joint development, joint ownership agreements must be established. Resources such as the European IPR Helpdesk provide guidance on this.
- **Access & Licensing:** Proper access rights must be ensured for background and foreground IP. Third-party components and licensing terms should be carefully considered.
- **Exploitation & IP Protection:** Beneficiaries must facilitate result exploitation for up to four years post-project, including further research, commercialization, and standardization. Periodic IP reviews and state-of-the-art assessments are recommended.
- **Safeguarding Foreground IP:** Each key exploitable result should be evaluated for protection through licensing, copyright, patents, or confidentiality measures to align with the exploitation strategy.
- **Consortium Agreement (CA):** Defines IP management rules, ensuring knowledge and IPR sharing among partners at no cost when required for project execution. Background knowledge remains the property of the disclosing partner.

All foreground IP (individual or jointly owned) will be assessed for provisional patent applications, enabling timely dissemination while maintaining accessibility for research institutions and industry. Since the consortium does not involve direct competitors, IP risks are minimized.

An IPR management plan has been developed and integrated into the Ethics and legal guidelines (D1.5).

5.2.1 Legal Framework

The OH-FINE consortium manages Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) in alignment with Horizon Europe principles, ensuring fair and open access to IP during and after the project. The Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA) define the use of background knowledge and project results, outlining ownership, access rights, and confidentiality where needed for commercialization.

- **Ownership & Access Rights:** Results belong to the partner generating them, while jointly developed outputs are co-owned. Institutions hold legal ownership of foreground IP, requiring collaboration with technology transfer offices for IP management.
- **PR Policies & Agreements:** The GA and CA outline ownership policies, exploitation rules, revenue-sharing, and conflict resolution. Partners have agreed on IP policies, ensuring necessary access rights.
- **Background Knowledge:** Partners share essential IP freely for project execution, while retaining ownership. Any exemptions must be listed in the Consortium Agreement.
- **Foreground IP & Exploitation:** Jointly developed IP will be protected and disseminated, benefiting academia and industry. IPR will be licensed within the project at no cost, with

further usage subject to agreement but unrestricted for research. No partner may unreasonably withhold essential technical information, except for explicitly excluded background IP.

5.3 Actions to develop

Exploitation activities in OH-FINE will continue throughout the project. The Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and risk assessment will be continuously updated, with potential new KERs added. The Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) strategy will be refined, including updates on related technologies, competitors, and patents. The next step involves defining the most suitable Business Model using tools such as the Business Model Canvas.

5.3.1 One-on-One Meetings with Partners

BET will facilitate individual meetings to help partners discuss:

- KERs advancement
- IPR handling
- Market introduction strategies

A questionnaire will be distributed to consortium members, and responses will be analysed in the OH-FINE Exploitation Workshop (Month 36).

5.3.2 OH-FINE Exploitation Workshop (Month 36)

This workshop will gather insights on transforming KERs into market-ready solutions. It includes:

- Introduction: Overview of key concepts for KER characterization.
- Discussion: Evaluation of significant KERs.
- Mapping: Creation of Risk Assessment and Priority Maps.

The workshop will group KERs for better discussions and explore joint exploitation opportunities through an integrated platform.

5.3.3 Intermediate Exploitation Plan (Month 36)

A step-by-step strategy to convert project results into practical tools and products, focusing on:

- Identifying potential key results
- Managing IPR
- Market introduction strategies

It will align with partners to ensure effective utilization and proper handling of intellectual property.

5.3.4 Final Exploitation Plan (Month 47)

A comprehensive economic and productive feasibility analysis will be conducted, including:

- Market analysis: SWOT assessment, commercialization strategies, and funding opportunities.
- Regulatory compliance: Legalization, certification, and adherence to EU standards.
- Production logistics: Scalability, infrastructure, and sustainability planning.
- Financial viability: Sensitivity analysis, profitability, cash flow, and revenue models.

The final plan will ensure the widespread adoption of OH-FINE's innovations, translating project outcomes into market-ready solutions that benefit multiple industries.

6. References

European Commission. (2024 a). Horizon Europe (HORIZON), HE Programme Guide, Version 4.1, 01 May 2024. European Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

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DRAFT

7. Annex 1: Communication Handbook

Author: Aina Calafat Rogers (SEAE)

This document contains guidelines for partners on different communication materials and activities as well as instructions on the use of the project and funding logos in all communication activities.

It also includes details about the project’s social media and considerations for communication activities through partner’s social media and communication channels

7.1 Visibility of the funding logo, flags and disclaimer

7.1.1 Funding logos

All communication and dissemination activities related to the project (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge the support received by both funders, the European Union (EU) and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

The European flag (emblem), the SERI logo and funding acknowledgements (translated into local languages, where appropriate) must be displayed according to the rules described below. For simplicity, we have created a file that includes both funder logos as well as the acknowledgments:

OH-FINE has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101183127 and by the Swiss State Secretariate for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 24.00503.

It can be downloaded in multiple languages from the SACO platform here: [SACO-platform > 03 Logos Templates > Logos > Funding-Logos](#)

EU Logo

The EU funding logo can be downloaded in all European languages at the following link: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

or

OH-FINE

EU Horizon Europe GA n° 101183127/ SERI Contract n° 24.00503

It may not be altered in any way. The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

As it will be displayed in association with other logos (SERI's and the partners' logos), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

The emblem may be used without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. However, this does not, give any right to exclusive use and no-one may appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo by registration or by any other means.

SERI Logo

The SERI logo can be downloaded in various formats at the following link: <https://www.sbf.admin.ch/sbf/en/home/seri/logo.html>

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

OR

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

The logo may not be altered in any way and the minimum size for print products is: 36.5 mm (portrait) wide or 66.5 mm (landscape) wide.

7.1.2 Funding acknowledgments

In addition to the two logos, all materials should include an acknowledgment of the funders, including the EU grant agreement number and the SERI contract number.

For example, in English it can say "This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101183127 and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 24.00503".

7.1.3 Disclaimer

Any communication activity must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into the language in which the material is displayed):

"Funded by the European Union and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union (EU) or the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Neither the EU nor SERI can be held responsible for them."

7.2 OH-FINE project's identity

Having an attractive visual identity will enable the project to seize the attention of the target audiences and expand its impact. The project's identity starts with a logo that can synthesize in an image the main concept of the project. In this sense, for the OH-FINE project, a leaf has been chosen to evoke the Euroleaf of the organic production logo. With a green gradient visually supporting the connection between the leaf and the speech bubble (evoking communication) also making it appear more three-dimensional. The gradient also symbolizes the conversion to organic farming. All communication materials will contain the project's logo, with the following characteristics

7.2.1 Logo

The OH-FINE logo should be used in all project-related materials. It is available in various formats.

Logo

protection zone:
the blue area around the logo
must remain free

Logo with claim

Logo Black

Logo White

In addition to the project logo and the logo of the funders, communication materials may include the logos of the project partner or of all the partners in the consortium.

The project logo can be found on the SACO platform in the following folder: [SACO-platform > 03 Logos Templates > Logo > OH-FINE Logo](#)

All the partners logos can be found on the SACO platform in the following folder: [SACO-platform > 03 Logos Templates > Logos > Partners Logos](#)

7.2.2 Colours

In addition to black, the project colours are outlined below. Other colours should be avoided in all project materials.

7.2.3 Fonts

The corporate typography has been established in line with the logo, and the templates and communication and dissemination materials, designed accordingly.

7.2.4 Templates

To facilitate the correct implementation of the design rules established for a common style and project identity, specific templates have been created. These will serve as practical tools for developing and designing the different communication materials.

- Word template for deliverables and milestones.
- Word template for short texts, letters, project notes, minutes
- PowerPoint template for presentations.

All of these templates can be found here: [SACO-platformt > 03 Logos Templates > Templates.](#)

7.3 Communication tools and materials

Information about the project, about organic farming and on the use of public funds will be promoted through social media campaigns, local community meetings, and the participation in fairs, exhibitions and other events.

Several materials will be designed and distributed aiming to raise awareness about the project and networking opportunities.

The goals are to engage at least 200 different stakeholders across Europe and to reach over 5,000 individuals through various communication channels making sure that at least 1,000 people attend in total across all dissemination events. Farmers participating in the Regional Hubs will contribute to identify and engage other farmers using the snowball strategy.

7.3.1 Communication materials

In order to inform stakeholders about the projects' objectives, activities and milestones, and engage stakeholders, different materials will be designed and spread using specific communication channels. These materials will be shared through the project's social media (at least LinkedIn and Instagram) in English. Partners existing communication channels such as their websites, social media and networks, will be used to enhance communication.

These materials will include at least:

- A poster/rollup describing the project's goals and activities through the different work packages and in the different countries, will be designed and translated to the project's countries languages. The poster will be printed and used in all in-person activities, as well as in the various events including the European Researchers Night and Science week.
- With the same intention, flyers will be designed in the languages of the project countries and distributed in both digital and printed versions.
- A promotional video describing the project's goals and activities, will be prepared in English and subtitled in all of the project partners' languages. The video will be shared on the project's social media and on the partners' social media to enhance the number of stakeholders reached and engaged.
- Press releases on all main activities and events organised and developed by the consortium will be published on the website and the projects' social media.
- Digital campaigns will be used to announce and promote the activities and main milestones.
- To engage target audiences, public factsheets on general aspects will also be released and shared.
- To ensure a more effective impact, infographics will be adapted to different target audiences and translated into the project's countries languages.

Both the poster and the flyer will have a QR code linking to the project's website to access the complete and detailed information displayed on <https://www.oh-fine.eu/>.

7.3.2 Communication Contact Points

To ensure effective coordination and impact of all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, every partner will identify a Communication Contact Point (CCP) whose contact data will be added to the CCP table on the SACO platform. CCP's will be responsible for keeping continuous contact with WP10-12 leaders, attending the quarterly WP10-12 meetings, sending WP10-12 leaders the news for the website and project's social media and reporting all the C&D activities registering in the correspondent tracker. They are also

responsible for translating communication and dissemination materials created at the project level into their regional languages and multiplying project information through their social media channels/websites. Finally, they will provide advice on best approaches to reach the respective target groups in their countries and networks and translate the documents and information into their languages

7.3.3 Project website

The project website will be the main information point for the project. It provides essential project details, news, publications, events and other resources to support sustainable organic agriculture. It will be translated into the project's countries languages and continuously updated.

The website is managed by FiBL CH in collaboration with SEAE and project partners. Partners are responsible for informing FiBL CH of all upcoming and past activities so they can be reflected on the website. Partners will also provide content for news items for the website.

All communication and dissemination materials will contain a QR Code or a link to the website <https://www.oh-fine.eu/> For more information about the website, see deliverable 10.1.

7.3.4 Social media channels

Throughout the project, at least the following social media platforms will be used:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/oh-fine/>
- Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/ohfine.euproject/>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@OH-FINE>

These will be managed in English. In addition, other suitable platforms will be created and managed in each regional hub in Spain, Ireland, Belgium, Bulgaria, Poland, Lithuania and Austria (by OFISET, TEAGASC, WULS, BIOSELENA, LEUA, FiBL AT, EV ILVO) to overcome language and cultural gaps for end-users. These platforms will contain at least what is published on the project's social media and information on the activities and events occurring in their country.

All partners will also make sure they use their own communication channels to communicate the project and its results widely, which will also include articles in the specialised press. The project relies heavily on all partners to use their established networks and communication channels and contacts in a very focused approach to reach the greatest possible reach in their country in a cost-effective way.

When communicating, partners will maintain consistency in the use of project logos, colors, and fonts, respecting the project's visual identity. Partners will also encourage the audience to learn more about the OH-FINE project, by tagging the project's social media channels and inviting them to visit the project website. When appropriate, they will also tag project partners, especially those involved in the task being communicated, as well as projects, or stakeholders that can be key to the project, opinion leaders, collaborators, etc. Relevant hashtags that include OH-FINE will be used, both to raise awareness and encourage their participation.

8. Annex 2: Dissemination Handbook

Authors: Laura Kemper and Barbara Schäfer (FiBL CH)

This document contains guidelines for partners on different dissemination materials and activities. It provides an overview of the different educational materials, scientific and non-scientific publications, OH-FINE events and general procedure that will be used in the project.

8.1 Sharing documents prior to publication

Partners must inform the consortium before publishing any project outputs or results.

According to the consortium agreement:

- “Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication” (p. 23).

According to the grant agreement:

- “A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate” (p.10).

We interpret this to mean:

- Any **publications that include results** (e.g. scientific publications) should be added to the [“04. Publications for review”](#) folder on the OH-FINE SACO platform at least **45 days prior to being made public**.
- Any **publications that include more general information** (e.g. communications materials, most technical documents, etc.) should be added to the [“04. Publications for review”](#) folder on the OH-FINE SACO platform at least **15 days prior to being made public**.

As a general rule, it is good to inform all partners that are involved in the topics included in your publications well in advance. This does not apply to social media posts. Partners should take care not to include any sensitive information in these posts.

8.2 Reporting tracker

A reporting tracker has been set up to keep track of all communication and dissemination activities. This will 1) help ensure we reach all communication and dissemination KPIs and 2) facilitate reporting by ensuring we can inform the European commission of all of the work we have done and demonstrate compliance with the project KPIs.

Partners are expected to fill in the required information in the three tables:

- **Conferences_Events_Meetings:** Partners should enter all required information for all events they attend or organise within the scope of the OH-FINE project.
- **Publications:** Partners should enter all required information for all publications that include results. Publications that simply inform about the project should be included in the communications tab (see below). All technical documents produced in WP5, 6 and 7 will be entered by FiBL CH or FiBL AT

- **Communications:** Partners should enter all required information for all communication activities. These are activities that simply inform the public or stakeholder groups about the project but do not include any results, training, etc.

The reporting tracker can be found in the OH-FINE_coordination_excel on the [SACO-platform](#)

8.3 Educational materials: Overview, KPIs, timelines, and workflows

A list of potential topics, timelines and partners responsible for the educational materials (technical documents and videos) will be established in work package 5 and 7 in 2025. These topics will be entered in a “**dissemination tracker**”, which will enable FiBL CH and FiBL AT to track progress and ensure all of the steps are carried out according to the procedures outlined below. The tracker can be found on the OH-FINE SACO platform here: [SACO-platform > WP10-11-12.Communication Dissemination](#).

The following sections provide an overview of the different educational materials, the KPIs, the responsibilities, key steps, timelines and important tips.

8.3.1 Technical documents (factsheets)

These documents should serve as practical tools to help target audiences with conversion and post-conversion. The main target audience for these technical documents is practitioners. Some technical documents may also be targeted toward advisors and other key actors helping with conversion to organic.

KPIs

- 10 technical documents related to conversion
- 5 technical documents related to post-conversion
- 26 technical documents related to field trials

Responsibilities

Partners:

- Draft in Word template
- Providing pictures/graphics
- Editing text based on revisions
- Reviewing translations into your language
- Disseminating through your work and in regional hubs

FiBL CH / FiBL AT:

- Text editing
- Layout
- Upload to the “04_Publications-for-review” folder on the SACO platform
- Prepare translations for partner review

- Upload to Organic Eprints, Zenodo, Organic Farm Knowledge, EU FarmBook, EU CAP Network and other relevant platforms

Contact person: Barbara Schaefer barbara.schaefer@fibl.org (FiBL CH) and Friedrich Leitgeb friedrich.leitgeb@fibl.org (FiBL AT).

Required working time

- First author: >3.5 working days (WD)
- Other authors and reviewers: 0.5 WD
- Editor (FiBL CH / FiBL AT): >3 WD

Key steps and timeline

The technical documents usually take at least 14 weeks to finalise. The procedure is as follows:

1. Authors: Draft text using the template and provide visuals
2. FiBL CH (WP5 and 6) or FiBL AT (WP7): Review and provide feedback
3. Authors and FiBL CH/FiBL AT: Revise draft to integrate feedback
4. WP lead (and other necessary partners): Review draft
5. Authors and FiBL CH/FiBL AT: Revise draft to integrate feedback
6. FiBL CH: Layout in project design
7. FiBL CH/FiBL AT: Add draft to the "[04 Publications for review](#)" folder on the OH-FINE SACO platform at least 15 days prior to publication
8. CSIC: Final check by coordination
9. FiBL CH: Publish final version on OH-FINE website, Zenodo, Organic Eprints, Organic Farm Knowledge, EU FarmBook, EU CAP Network and other relevant platforms
10. FiBL CH: Circulate AI-translations among partners responsible for translation
11. Partners: Check and finalise translations in their languages
12. FiBL CH: Publish translations on OH-FINE website, Zenodo, Organic Eprints, Organic Farm Knowledge, EU FarmBook, EU CAP Network and other relevant platforms
13. SEAE: Post on OH-FINE social media
14. Regional hubs: post on social media and circulate within your networks
15. All partners: post on institution social media and use and disseminate final product

Important tips when drafting technical documents

- Keep target audience in mind: What do they need to know? What is interesting to them?
- Visuals: always include several pictures and/or other illustrations that help to explain the information in the technical document. They should be high quality and should always include a source (at least the name of the person who took the picture and the year).

- Include links to additional resources that will allow users to get a full picture.

Template

- OH-FINE technical document template – [SACO-platform > 03 Logos Templates > Templates > Videos Technical-documents](#)

8.3.2 Practice abstracts

Practice abstracts will be made based on the technical documents and uploaded on the OH-FINE page on the EU CAP Network website: https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/organic-farming-innovations-network-europe_en

This process will be managed by FiBL-CH in coordination with the partners responsible for each technical document.

KPIs

- 40 practice abstracts

8.3.3 Videos

Videos should serve as practical tools to help target audiences with conversion and post-conversion. This can be done by answering common questions, giving different perspectives, providing insights on tools or techniques, etc.

Videos can have different formats, depending on the purpose and target audience. More information about video formats, preparation and concept creation, equipment, and editing is available in section 8.6.

The main target audience for the OH-FINE videos is practitioners. Some videos may also be targeted toward advisors and other key actors helping with conversion to organic.

KPIs

- 30 dissemination videos
- 26 videos of field trials
- Of these:
 - 23 videos. Duration: 1m and 30". 15" versions of each video will be made for permanent dissemination on social media: Meta, Twitter and TikTok. Total views: 120.000.
 - At least 10 videos on advanced organic techniques and organic marketing
 - Around 20 videos on conversion to organic

Responsibilities

Partners:

- Drafting storyboard to plan out the video
- Recording video footage

- Ensure everyone visible in the video has signed a consent form – see templates below
- Editing video (where possible)
- Reviewing translation of subtitles (where applicable)
- Disseminating through your work

FiBL CH / FiBL AT:

- Technical support (guidelines, training, standardized look and feel)
- Support with storyboard and upload to the “04_Publications-for-review” on the SACO platform once drafted
- Editing video (where necessary)
- Upload to OH-FINE YouTube channel, Organic Farm Knowledge, EU CAP Network and other relevant platforms
- Manage subtitles on YouTube and other platforms
- Prepare video shorts/reels for social media (where relevant)

Contact person: Barbara Schaefer barbara.schaefer@fibl.org (FiBL CH) and Friedrich Leitgeb friedrich.leitgeb@fibl.org (FiBL AT).

Required working time

- Concept and organisation of the video shoot: >1 working day (WD)
- Video recording: 1 WD
- Video editing: >1 WD

Key steps and timelines

It usually takes at least 14 weeks for a video to be produced. The procedure is as follows:

1. Partner: Draft storyboard using template
2. FiBL CH (WP5 and 6) or FiBL AT (WP7): Review storyboard and provide feedback
3. FiBL CH/FiBL AT: Upload storyboard to the “04_Publications for review” folder on the [“04_Publications for review”](#) folder on the OH-FINE SACO platform at least two weeks prior to filming
4. Partner: Record footage (see video guidelines in section 8.6 for tips)
5. Partner: Edit footage into a video or send organised footage to FiBL CH/FiBL AT to edit.
6. FiBL CH/FiBL AT: Edit footage or review video sent by partner
7. Partner and FiBL CH/FiBL AT: Finalise video
8. CSIC: Final check by coordinator
9. FiBL CH: Publish on OH-FINE website, YouTube channel, EU FarmBook, Organic Farm Knowledge and EU CAP Network

10. FiBL CH/FiBL AT: Circulate AI-translations of subtitles among partners responsible for translation
11. Partners: Check and finalise translations in their languages
12. FiBL CH: Publish translated subtitles on relevant channels
13. SEAE: Post on OH-FINE social media
14. Regional hubs: post on social media and disseminate in your networks
15. All partners: post on institution social media and use and disseminate final product

Important tips

- Keep target audience in mind when writing storyboard: What do they need to know? What is interesting to them?
- Planning out the storyboard in advance will make all subsequent steps much easier
- Ensure everyone who appears on the video has signed the OH-Fine Image Consent Form (link to template below)
- Film in landscape view if using a smartphone
- See section 8.6 for more detailed video guidelines

Templates

- The “OH-FINE video storyboard template” and the “OH-FINE first and last slide template”: [SACO-platform > 03 Logos Templates > Templates > Videos Technical-documents](#)
- OH-FINE Image Consent Form template: [SACO-platform > 03 Logos Templates > Templates](#)

8.3.4 Policy briefs

Policy briefs are short documents that present findings and recommendations of a research project to government policymakers and others, who are interested in formulating or influencing policy.

There are two types of policy briefs:

- Advocacy briefs that argue in favour of a particular course of action
- Objective briefs that provide balanced information
- 3 policy briefs with recommendations for policy makers to influence future policy and regulatory actions will be elaborated compiling the main conclusions of the project and presented to the correspondent competent authorities.

KPIs

- 3 policy briefs
- Guide with conclusions and recommendations

- At least 3 major policy recommendations adopted, with engagement from 25+ policymakers

Responsibilities

This task will be lead by SEAE, but the contents will be elaborated together with TEAGASC, AFOA, BIOSELENA, LEUA, MESETARIA and FiBL AT as follows:

1. Definition of the outcomes to be included; all partners involved in this task
2. First draft of the policy brief by SEAE
3. Reviewing by all partners involved in the task and content
4. Second draft of the policy brief by SEAE
5. Upload to the "04_Publications-for-review" folder on the SACO platform
6. Reviewing by all partners involved in the task
7. Final version editing and layout by SEAE
8. Translation by partners if relevant for local contexts
9. FiBL CH: Publication on the OH-FINE website, Zenodo, Organic Eprints, EU FarmBook, the EU CAP Network and other relevant platforms
10. SEAE: Post on OH-FINE social media channels
11. Sending to competent authorities: CSIC and SEAE will be responsible, but project partners can contribute contacting their national competent authorities.
12. Regional hubs: post on social media and circulate within your networks

Required working time

- First author: >5 working days
- Other authors and reviewers: 1 WD
- Editor (SEAE): >2 WD

Timeline

The contents of the policy briefs will be prepared from the outcomes of the project's activities from the very beginning, but they will be finally produced between month 36 and month 48.

8.3.5 Other KPIs related to the educational materials

- Produce and distribute at least 50 different types of materials, reaching at least 5,000 producers
- OH-FINE contents, materials and actions: user satisfaction >80%, indicating high usability and relevance of the models (surveys)
- Produce a minimum of 30 comprehensive dissemination documents, each receiving at least 500 downloads/views and 10 citations

- Dissemination reach: aim for an audience reach of over 1,000 individuals across at least 5 different EU countries, with engagement metrics like downloads, shares, or active participation in events
- Reaching at least 2,000 people through various channels

8.4 Scientific and non-scientific publications

Scientific publications refer primarily to peer-reviewed journal articles. These should be targeted toward the scientific community. **All manuscripts must be uploaded to the “[04 Publications for review](#)” folder on the SACO platform at least 45 days before they are submitted** to the journal. This is to give partners the opportunity to ensure that potentially sensitive results can be protected.

Non-scientific publications include articles in farmers magazines or other specialised press, among other formats. These can serve to make target audiences aware of the project as well as OH-FINE outputs, results, events, etc.

Scientific and non-scientific publications **must acknowledge the funding** from the European Union, including the grant agreement number. Ideally, they will also acknowledge funding from the Swiss funding organisation. For example:

“These results were produced in the OH-FINE project, funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under the grant agreement No 101183127 and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation under contract number 24.00503”.

Where partners cannot control the final text (e.g. media articles), please communicate our funding requirements to the publishers.

Where possible, the logos of the funders should also be included. These are available on the SACO platform here: [SACO-platform > 03 Logos Templates > Funding logos](#)

All scientific publications should be recorded in the **reporting tracker** in the “Publications” table ([see OH-FINE coordination excel](#)). All publications that do not include project results should be recorded in the tracker in the “communications activities” tab. This will facilitate reporting of these publications.

KPIs

- 15 articles in specialised press (e.g. farmer’s magazines)
- A minimum of 3 peer-reviewed papers published

8.5 OH-FINE events

Different events will have different requirements. These will be defined within the various work packages and regional hubs based on the needs of the events. The relevant work packages are responsible for planning and carrying out the events. Planning and tracking documents should include the following points:

- **Inform WP10/11/12** before the event so we can post on social media before/after the event and include a news item on the website. If specific dissemination or communication materials are required, they can often be organised with enough notice.
- Advertise the event through regional hubs and/or partners' institutional networks
- All events should be recorded in the **reporting tracker** in the "Conferences_events_meetings" table ([see OH-FINE coordination excel](#)). This will facilitate reporting of these events.

For all events, some additional things should be taken into consideration:

- All events organised by the project should have a **sign-in sheet** where participants can register. These can include permission for taking pictures and receiving project updates (see following points).
- It is always a good idea to take **pictures/videos of the event**. Please note: If people are recognisable in photos/videos, you may only publish them if there is prior consent. To address this, you can ask participants to provide consent as part of a sign in sheet.
- Event participants interested in the project can **sign up to stay up-to-date** about the project via the website. Alternatively, you can include a box to check on the sign-in sheet if they are interested. If you then send the sign-in sheet to FiBL CH, we can add them to the distribution list.

More specific guidelines and information will be defined within the respective work packages and regional hubs.

Event KPIs

- 26 technical workshops: will be done within task 5.2. Contact: SEAE
- 26 field demonstrations: will be done within task 7.3. Contact: EV ILVO
- 30 meetings among producers: will be done as part of task 5.5 and 6.5. Contact: AFOA
- 8 cross visits: will be done within task 5.7 and 6.7. Contact: FiBL AT
- Participation in 4 Agricultural fairs
- 3 Fora: will be done within task 3.3 with ≥ 50 attendees at each one. Contact: EV ILVO
- 20 Co-creative and co-decision sessions with diverse representation of stakeholders (OFC + RKH) – WP3 and WP7
- At least 10 joint initiatives or partnerships
- 5 Collaborative workshops, seminars or meetings (with EIP Operational groups and other projects) – Tasks 5.8, 6.8 and 10.6. Contacts: OFISET and TEAGASC
- Ensure at least 1,000 attendees in total across all dissemination events
- European Researchers Night & Science: 5 universities
- Science week: 8 events, one per EU country.
- OH-FINE contents, materials, and actions: user satisfaction $>80\%$, indicating high usability and relevance of the models (surveys)

8.5.1 Cross visits

The OH-FINE project includes an impactful farmer exchange programme, encompassing eight cross visits to take advantage of the experience and knowledge of each partner. The visits will foster a hands-on learning experience by enabling farmers to visit and observe farming practices in different countries. The cross visits will be organised by FiBL AT, CSIC/SEAE, FiBL CH, LAMMC, TEAGASC, EV ILVO, WULS and FCI Chirpan as part of tasks 5.7 and 6.7.

FiBL AT is leading these tasks and produced a manual for the partners organising the cross visits, which will be available here once it is ready: [SACO-platform > WP5-6.Capacity Building Information Cross-fertilisation > Cross-visits > Manual](#)

These visits are collaborative field trips involving a mix of researchers, advisors and farmers who spend two to four days in a given region. The basic aim is to inspire and educate, rather than to provide an in-depth, comprehensive assessment of a particular knowledge and innovation system. Instead, the focus remains on stimulating ideas and fostering understanding.

The host partner plays a crucial role in organising the cross visit, selecting potential cases for observation and handling the logistics. This includes organising farm and site visits, facilitating meetings with key actors, securing venues for discussions, providing catering, planning social events and arranging transport - all supported by the host partner's budget. They also act as the main facilitator, using interactive learning methods to ensure effective information gathering and time management.

In order to prepare participants, a document is circulated beforehand containing details of the region's organic farming background, key themes and descriptions of each innovation case. This helps visitors understand what to expect and helps them prepare. It is important for both visitors and hosts to understand the nature of cross visits, which involves active questioning and keeping general presentations concise.

During each visit, three to five innovation cases are explored. Each partner participates in at least six out of the eight cross visits. While these visits provide only a snapshot of each innovation case and do not claim to be exhaustive, they provide valuable impressions and inspire participants to further explore innovation in organic farming.

8.6 Video Guidelines

8.6.1 Video styles

Tutorials are filmed outdoors or in indoor facilities such as laboratories. Tutorials use a voice-over as a narrator. These technical clips show how something is done, e.g., by actors demonstrating a new sampling method.

Lecture-style videos are realised in front of a green screen and show the narrator at least in parts of the video. They are structured similarly to tutorials and include additional information e.g., background information, why a new sampling method is required, the results of comparing the new with the old sampling method, etc.

Story-telling in PowerPoint or CapCut is structured similarly to tutorials, but instead of a video, pictures, illustrations, and short video clips are used in a PowerPoint presentation /

animated slide show of the software CapCut. There is always a voice-over instead of a shown narrator.

Explainer videos can be produced with several budget friendly or free software. They present an idea, concept, and process visually. Like in story-telling videos, there is always a voice-over instead of a shown narrator.

8.6.2 Preparing a video

The basic information for producing videos is described below. WP10 also organised a webinar at the beginning of the project to provide partners with basic information about making videos. The recording of the webinar and the slides can be found here: [SACO Platform > WP10-11-12.Communication Dissemination > Guides-handbooks > Video-training](#)

For more information about best practices in video making in agriculture, see the following resources:

- Alföldi et al. (2019): Video production for agriculture, a guide for farmers, advisors and researchers. Available at: https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/37544/1/alfoldi-et-al-2019-Videoguide_EN_25June2019.pdf
- Hardy et al. Guidelines for Video Development. Available at <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/demo-design-guide-for-virtual-demonstrations/>

8.6.3 Choose a production team

For almost all projects, a 2-person crew (1 director and 1 camera operator) is the basic set-up. They provide two sets of eyes to decide which shots are needed. The director leads the shoot, guides the speakers, and makes sure everything is going according to plan. The camera operator can focus on the sound and picture quality. Most projects will require at least 1 presenter. This can be an additional person, as shown in the video. It can also be done as a voice-over. There can also be the main narrator (shown or voice-over) and several other speakers (shown or voice-over) that give statements or explain details.

8.6.4 Structuring the content

Once the topic is agreed upon, it should be narrowed down, and the most important points the video wants to get across to the audience should be written down. Then these points can be formulated in sentences. As a rule of thumb: 100 words make 1 minute of film. The basic structure consists of:

- **The intro** starts with 2 seconds of information on the project in a standardized look (see template). Afterward, the theme and its relevance are presented. Additionally, the main speaker and the location are introduced. The viewer usually decides within the first 30 seconds if the video is worth watching!
- **The main part** presents solutions, recommendations and the main messages of the video. This part can be divided into sub-chapters.
- **The outro** draws a short conclusion, refers to further information, and ends with another freeze frame of the project information (10 seconds, use template) (see template)

Intro and outro slide templates: [SACO-platform > 03 Logos Templates > Templates > Videos Technical-documents](#)

8.6.5 Planning your storyboard

A video should be planned at a content (speech) level and on an image level, regardless of whether the content is narrated by a presenter or by a voice-over. This is often called a storyboard. The content level is the A-roll. The image level is referred to as B-roll. Once the text for the narrator is written, the director has to plan the appropriate images that complement the text. B-roll can be video material, but also good photos or illustrations.

OH-FINE video storyboard template – [SACO-platform > 03 Logos Templates > Templates > Videos Technical-documents](#)

8.6.6 Equipment

It is advisable to test the equipment before the recording day.

- **Camera:** Camcorders or cameras with video functions are designed for filming. But smartphones usually also have an excellent camera built in. **Always record in the landscape with the smartphone** and switch the phone to airplane mode, so no notifications can disturb the recording.
- **Microphone:** Built-in microphones of smartphones are usually sufficient for quiet environments. If the video is shot outside or there is ambient noise, an external microphone should be used for smartphones or video cameras. If used outside, external lavalier and handheld microphones should be protected by a windshield (fur). Wireless lavalier microphones offer the possibility to move around freely and use hands to show and demonstrate things, but also handheld microphones are a possibility. It is important to always check the sound via headphones.
- **Tripod:** Most newer smartphones have image stabilization, which prevents overly shaky videos. Still, where possible, a tripod should be used to keep images stable. There are simple rigs for smartphones available for around 20 euros. These rigs can be mounted on a tripod. Gimbals are more expensive but produce soft and dynamic movements (“steady cam”).

8.6.7 Ethics (Consent)

Before filming, the EU data protection regulations require that you obtain free and informed consent from those who will be filmed. Consent can be given by completing a short, targeted, informed consent form ensuring that the participant has understood the use of the images, knows they can withdraw consent at any time, and retains the right to the footage although they allow the project to use the data captured or processed.

See the OH-FINE image consent form template: [SACO-platform > 03 Logos Templates > Templates](#)

8.6.8 A-roll: Tips for recordings

- **Relaxed atmosphere** between the production team and filmed persons. External disturbance during filming should be avoided.
- **Sitting or standing:** Usually, presenters should stand. Only long interviews should be recorded sitting.
- **Image composition:** The eye line should lie on the upper third of the image (see image below).

- **Direction of sight:** The main presenter and additional presenters who explain something to the audience should look directly into the camera. Only for interviews should the interviewee look slightly laterally past the camera (into the eyes of the interviewer, which is positioned next to the camera but not shown in the shot).
- **Do not turn off the camera:** Let the camera roll during the entire recording time. This avoids missing statements that can be included in the video. Frames that are not needed can be deleted in post-production.
- **Silent nodding:** During the recording, the focus is on the presenter and content. To avoid intermediate remarks from the interviewer or director, communicate non-verbally, e.g., by nodding.
- **Crisp statements:** Most people cannot describe something concisely and precisely. Therefore, plan at least two takes. The first one serves to reduce nervousness, and the second one focuses on precise statements. Writing down the main points that should be presented in the concept can help.
- **Integrate the question into the answer:** If the questions of the interviewer will be cut out in post-production, the interviewee must integrate the keyword so that viewers can follow the context.

8.6.9 B-roll: Ensure varied image settings

The images should already be roughly defined in the storyboard. The individual clips should at least be 30 sec long, without zoom and pans. Examples of B-roll clips are:

- **Long shots to open a scene:** At the beginning, it is recommended to give the viewer an overview of the scene when filmed in an outdoor location or indoors, when the setting is important (e.g., a lab). A long shot from the ground or if possible, from a higher vantage point is suitable for this purpose.

- **Medium long shot:** A shot that shows an overview of the scene. If used frequently or for too long, these shots can get boring.
- **Details, close-ups:** Long shots should be supplemented with close-ups. Either they start to form a long shot and zoom in (on a mobile phone, it is not easy to do that smoothly and needs some practice), or they are recorded separately, already starting to zoom in on an important detail.
- **Additional image material:** Additional material can be farmers/scientists in conversation, hands on the ground/with a pipette, plants with their roots, etc.

8.6.10 Editing the video

Editing can be challenging and requires some practice. If you and your organisation do not have any experience with editing, FiBL CH (WP5 and 6) or FiBL AT (WP7) can support you with this.

8.7 Zenodo

Zenodo is an open-access repository. All OH-FINE publications (scientific and non-scientific) will be uploaded to Zenodo and affiliated with the OH-FINE community.

Note: There is no OH-FINE community. Instead, partners use their personal accounts to upload documents and then link them to the OH-FINE community.

The OH-FINE community can be found here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/oh-fine/>

All new entries will be checked by FiBL CH and accepted to the community.

Uploading to Zenodo

1. Login your Zenodo account
2. Click on “New upload”
3. Click on “Select a community” and start typing “OH-FINE”. The community should appear with the logo.
4. Import the file(s) by dragging it/them into the appropriate field or by clicking “upload files”

5. Under “Basic information”, you can fill in relevant keywords, such as:

- Work package tags: OH-FINE_WP1, OH-FINE_WP2, etc.
- Format: OH-FINE_TD (Technical document), OH-FINE_PB (policy brief), OH-FINE_Video, etc.
- Themes, Crops, etc.

Note: To add more than 1 keyword, click on “Add another keyword”, otherwise they will all appear together as one keyword.

1. Under “Funding” click “Add”. In the pop-up screen, enter the grant agreement number – 101183127 – and click on OH-FINE and then “Add”.

2. Fill in the other relevant information
3. Once everything has been entered, click “Save” at the bottom of the page
4. Before you click “Publish” at the bottom, make sure that your document is the final version.

Note: once a file has been published you cannot delete it, but you can edit the metadata or add a new version (see below for instructions).

Editing a record (to edit metadata only)

You can edit the metadata (title, creators, etc) of a published record at any time:

1. Open the record and click the orange “Edit” button
2. Make required changes and click “Save” and “Publish”

Uploading a new version of a document

You cannot delete files from Zenodo, but you can add a new version. The new version will have a new DOI a new hyperlink:

1. Open the record
2. Click on “New version”

3. The deposit form will now show that you're editing a **New version draft**. Fill in the metadata, upload files as for any other record.

Responsibilities

Partners:

- Create a Zenodo account
- Upload peer-reviewed publications, publications in non-scientific magazines, conference presentations and other relevant materials.

FiBL CH:

- Review submissions and accept them to the community
- Upload OH-FINE technical documents, and other educational materials
- Upload support for partners
- Contact person: Barbara Schaefer barbara.schaefer@fibl.org

SEAE:

- Upload all OH-FINE communication materials

8.8 Organic Eprints

General instructions for Organic Eprints are available in English, French, Spanish, Portuguese, Czech and Turkish here: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/29427/>

Important: when adding a document, don't forget to affiliate it with OH-FINE (see figure Figure 1).

Figure 1: Screenshot of Organic Eprints showing how to affiliate an entry with the OH-FINE project

Responsibilities

Partners:

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